

ASSESSMENT OF PMFBY (PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA) IN NANDED DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

Agriculture is a cornerstone of India's economy, employing 44% of the population and contributing 18.3% to GDP. However, the sector faces risks like natural disasters, pests, diseases, and climate change, leading to significant crop losses. To mitigate these risks, the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) was launched in 2016, providing crucial agricultural insurance. This study analyzes the growth and impact of PMFBY from 2016-17 to 2022-23, focusing on income stability among insured farmers, implementation challenges, and recommendations for improvement in Nanded district, Maharashtra. A total of 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers were surveyed across four talukas and three villages per taluka. The analysis revealed a national decline in the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of insured farmers, with -7% for kharif and -2% for rabi seasons. In contrast, Maharashtra saw a 20% increase in kharif, and Nanded experienced a slight 2% rise. While income stability improved under PMFBY, with a rise in mean income and decreased variability, challenges like insufficient and delayed payouts were noted. Farmers emphasized the need for timely and adequate compensation to enhance the scheme. Recommendations include improving coverage, ensuring timely claims settlements, and increasing transparency to boost participation and effectiveness. Despite growth in regions like Maharashtra, there is a concerning decline in crop insurance adoption nationally, especially during the rabi season. Issues such as inadequate compensation, delayed payouts, and poor crop assessments highlight weaknesses in PMFBY. However, the scheme has positively impacted income stability for insured farmers. Farmers advocated for timely compensation, broader crop coverage, and better transparency to foster trust and encourage wider adoption of crop insurance.

Keywords: PMFBY, CAGR, income stability, challenges

Introduction

Agriculture is a cornerstone of the Indian economy, contributing approximately 18.2% to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and providing livelihoods for around 42.3% of the population. Its vital role in economic planning is underscored by the historical development of crop insurance in the country, currently, two key schemes stand out: the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) and the Restructured Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (RWBCIS). Both schemes play crucial roles in safeguarding farmers' interests and providing essential risk management tools against financial losses due to crop failures. Launched in 2016, the PMFBY is a comprehensive yield-based policy designed to compensate farmers for production-related losses. It covers both pre-sowing and post-harvest losses caused by adverse weather conditions, addressing the critical need for income stabilization among farmers. PMFBY has been recognized as a pivotal agricultural insurance scheme in India, significantly impacting millions of farmers nationwide. Studying its implementation, effectiveness, and socio-economic implications offers valuable insights into its role in enhancing farmers' welfare and promoting agricultural resilience. The scheme aims not only to provide essential crop insurance but also to stabilize farmers' incomes, reduce their debt burden, and improve overall livelihood sustainability. This study will delve into the specifics of the PMFBY, exploring its progress, the roles of various insurance agencies, and its impact on income stability for farmers. By identifying areas for improvement in its implementation, the findings will contribute to understanding the broader implications of agricultural insurance in promoting sustainable farming practices and supporting the economic well-being of rural communities across India.

Methodology

The Nanded district was chosen for this study. Four talukas were selected, in each of the 12 selected villages, a random survey was conducted involving 10 insured farmers and 10 non-insured farmers, leading to a total sample size of 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers. Data collection occurred during the kharif season of 2023, incorporating both primary and secondary sources. The analysis of the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) primarily utilized secondary data obtained from reports of the Agriculture Insurance Company of India Limited and various government websites to evaluate PMFBY's growth over time. Key indicators analyzed included the number of

insured farmers, total area insured, claims data, and beneficiaries from 2016-17 to 2022-23. The CAGR was estimated using the following formulas.

$$Y_1 = a.b^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable for which growth rate is to be estimated (Number of farmer insured / Area insured / Reported claim / Approved claim / Total claim paid / Total farmer benefitted)

t = Time variable

b = Regression coefficient

a = Intercept

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } y = \text{log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots(2)$$

Then the per cent compound growth rate (r) was computed using the equation.

$$\text{CGR } (r) = [\text{Antilog } (\text{log } b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots(3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze income, including mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation (CV), and Income Stability Index. The Income Stability Index was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Income Stability Index} = 1 - \text{CV}$$

indicating income stability for both insured and non-insured farmers. The CV and income stability index allowed for a comparative analysis of income variation and stability between the two groups.

For identifying implementation weaknesses, Garrett's Ranking Technique was applied. Farmers ranked various challenges, and the ranks were converted into scores using Garrett's Table. Convert the ranks into Garrett scores using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent Position} = \left(\frac{R_{ij} - 0.5}{N_j} \right) \times 100$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} factor by the j^{th} individual

N_j = Number of factors ranked by the j^{th} individual

These scores were then averaged to identify the most significant issues affecting PMFBY implementation in Jalna district.

Result and Discussion**1 Progress of PMFBY in India, Maharashtra and Nanded district****1.1 Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Insured farmers**

Insured farmers under crop insurance schemes varies by region and season. Nationally, kharif season shows a decline of -7 per cent per annum, and rabi season a decline of -2 per cent per annum, both significant at the 5 per cent per annum level. In Maharashtra, kharif sees a positive CAGR of 20 per cent per annum, while rabi grows

modestly at 3 per cent per annum. Conversely, Nanded experiences a kharif increase of 2 per cent per annum but a sharp decline of -15 per cent per annum in rabi. These variations indicate the need for targeted interventions to enhance crop insurance coverage, particularly during the rabi season, to provide better financial protection for farmers.

Table 1: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Insured farmers from year 2016-2023

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi	
1	India	CAGR t value	-7%** -1.98	-2%** -0.62
2	Maharashtra	CAGR t value	20% 2.98	3%** 0.25
3	Nanded	CAGR t value	2%** 0.29	-15%** -0.64

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area Insured

Insured area under crop insurance schemes highlights regional and seasonal coverage variations. Nationally, the CAGR for both kharif and rabi seasons is 1 per cent per annum, indicating a modest but consistent increase in insured area, significant at the 5 per cent per annum level. Maharashtra shows a substantial kharif increase of 19 per cent per

annum, while rabi growth is 4 per cent per annum, reflecting higher demand for insurance in kharif due to rainfall dependence. In Nanded, the kharif CAGR is stable at 0 per cent per annum, with a slight rabi increase of 2 per cent per annum. Overall, while some regions exhibit growth, the national expansion remains limited, necessitating targeted interventions to improve coverage.

Table 2: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area of insured farmers from year 2016-2023

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi	
1	India	CAGR t value	1%** 0.51	1%** 0.34
2	Maharashtra	CAGR t value	19%** 1.34	4%** 0.29
3	Nanded	CAGR t value	0%** 0.002	2%** 0.38

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported claim

Reported claims under crop insurance schemes show significant regional and seasonal variations. In India, kharif claims rise by 8 per cent per annum annually, while rabi claims surge by 44 per cent per annum, with only the rabi increase statistically significant. This suggests higher crop risks in rabi, likely due to adverse weather or

lower crop resilience. In Maharashtra, kharif claims decline by 41 per cent per annum annually, while rabi claims grow by just 1 per cent per annum. In contrast, Nanded sees kharif claims rise by 12 per cent per annum annually, with rabi growing by 2 per cent per annum. These trends underscore the need for timely claim settlements and season-specific risk management strategies.

Table 3: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported Claim from year 2016-2023

Sr. No.	Particulars	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi	
1		India	CAGR t value	8% 2.41	44%** 1.75
2	Reported claim	Maharashtra	CAGR t value	-41%** -1.52	1%**** 0.04
3		Nanded	CAGR t value	12%** 2.31	2%** 0.1

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved claim

Approved claims under crop insurance schemes show significant declines across regions and seasons. Nationally, kharif claims dropped by -60 per cent per annum annually and rabi by -26 per cent per annum, both statistically significant. This suggests stricter approval processes or verification challenges, raising concerns about system inefficiencies. In Maharashtra, kharif claims fell by -42 per cent per

annum annually, while rabi claims rose slightly by 3 per cent per annum. However, Nanded saw kharif claims grow by 12 per cent per annum and rabi by 1 per cent per annum, indicating a more efficient process locally. The overall decline in approved claims, particularly in kharif, highlights the need for policy improvements and better verification processes to ensure timely approvals.

Table 4: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved Claim from year 2016-2023

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi	
1	India	CAGR t value	-60%** -2.47	-26%** -0.84
2	Maharashtra	CAGR t value	-42%** -1.57	3%** 0.11
3	Nanded	CAGR t value	12%** 2.23	1%** 0.7

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid

Total claims paid under crop insurance schemes show notable financial disbursement trends. Nationally, claims paid dropped by -5 per cent per annum annually in kharif and -20 per cent per annum in rabi, both statistically significant, suggesting stricter verifications or fewer approved claims, potentially causing farmer dissatisfaction. In

Maharashtra, kharif claims paid grew by 7 per cent per annum annually, while rabi claims declined by -13 per cent per annum. In contrast, Nanded saw strong growth, with kharif claims rising by 30 per cent per annum and rabi by 21 per cent per annum, indicating efficient claim settlements. These national declines, particularly in rabi, highlight concerns about the effectiveness of the schemes,

emphasizing the need for improved payouts to boost farmer confidence and financial protection.

Table 5: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid from year 2016-2023

Sr. No.	Particulars	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi	
1		India	CAGR t value	-5%** -1.01	-20%** -2.35
2	Total claim paid	Maharashtra	CAGR t value	7%** 0.83	-13%** -0.55
3		Nanded	CAGR t value	30%** 0.66	21%** 0.22

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total farmers benefit

The number of farmers benefiting from crop insurance schemes shows significant regional and seasonal variations. Nationally, beneficiaries have declined by -6 per cent per annum annually during kharif and -19 per cent per annum during rabi, both statistically significant. This suggests serious challenges in accessibility and effectiveness, with fewer farmers receiving financial protection due to delays or reduced

participation. In Maharashtra, kharif saw slight growth of 1 per cent per annum annually, but rabi declined sharply by -19 per cent per annum. In contrast, Nanded experienced strong growth, with beneficiaries increasing by 16 per cent per annum annually in kharif and 29 per cent per annum in rabi, reflecting successful scheme implementation. These national declines, especially in rabi, call for policy improvements to enhance access and benefits.

Table 6: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total farmer benefit from year 2016-2023

Sr. No.	Particulars	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi	
1		India	CAGR t value	-6%** -3.02	-19%** -2.41
2	Total farmers benefit	Maharashtra	CAGR t value	1%** 0.11	-19%** -0.73
3		Nanded	CAGR t value	16%** 0.34	29%** 0.76

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Impact of PMFBY on income stability of farmer

The analysis of gross income with and without compensation highlights the significant role of insurance payouts in stabilizing agricultural income for insured farmers. From 2016 to 2023, farmers' average gross income without compensation was ₹171,308.30, with a high standard deviation of ₹57,784.61 and a coefficient of variation (CV) of 0.33, indicating moderate income instability. With

compensation, the average income increased to ₹185,103, and the CV dropped to 0.28, showing reduced income variability. The income stability index rose from 0.66 to 0.71 with compensation, confirming improved financial security. Overall, the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) significantly enhanced income stability for farmers in Nanded district during 2016-17 to 2022-23.

Table 7: Gross income stability and income index of sample insured farmers from year 2016-17 to 2022-23

Particulars	Gross income without compensation	Gross income with compensation
Standard Deviation	57784.61	52442.1
Mean	171308.3	185103
Coefficient of Covariation	0.33	0.28
Income stability Index	0.66	0.71

Weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and measures for its improvement

Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY

The analysis of constraints in adopting the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) among insured farmers, ranked using Garrett's method, identified several key issues. The top concern was insufficient compensation (Rank I, Mean Score: 76.51), leading to dissatisfaction and reluctance to adopt the scheme. Delays in compensation payments (Rank II, Mean Score: 70.43) caused financial strain, eroding trust. Inaccurate crop loss assessments due to lack of experts (Rank III, Mean

Score: 60.30) and poor coordination between banks and farmers (Rank IV, Mean Score: 58.5) further hampered the process. Frequent policy changes (Rank V, Mean Score: 50.83), delayed claim disbursements (Rank VI, Mean Score: 47.58), and lack of updates on digital portals (Rank VII, Mean Score: 36.97) added to the challenges. Trust issues (Rank VIII, Mean Score: 32.03), uncertainty about compensation (Rank IX, Mean Score: 31.83), and corruption in assessments (Rank X, Mean Score: 22.76) compounded farmers' reluctance. These findings highlight the need for significant improvements in PMFBY's implementation to address these concerns and boost participation.

Table 8: Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample Insured farmers

Sr. no.	Constraints	Mean	Garrett's Rank
1	Insufficient coordination of banks and farmers	58.5	IV
2	Insufficient compensation under PMFBY	76.51	I
3	Delay in realization of compensation	70.43	II
4	Corruption while assessment and settling claims	22.76	X
5	Frequent change in policy terms or condition create confusion while claim settlement	50.83	V
6	Experts are unavailable for assessment of crop loss	60.30	III
7	Claim should be dispersed before starting of next season	47.58	VI
8	Hard to trust the scheme due to past experience	32.03	VIII

9	Even after assessment by agency there is no assurance of compensation	31.83	IX
10	PMFBY Portals should be updated to access the claim details	36.97	VII

Suggestions given by sample Insured farmers

Insured farmers offered several key suggestions to improve the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), ranked by frequency. The most common recommendation, made by 88 farmers (73.33%), was for timely compensation, as delays impacted financial stability. Adequate compensation reflecting actual losses was second, suggested by 73 farmers (60.83%). Uniform indemnity across regions and crops, proposed by 63 farmers (52.50%), aimed to address compensation disparities. Additionally, 59 farmers (49.17%) recommended settling claims before the next season to ease financial pressure. Price guarantees were suggested by 47 farmers (39.17%) to protect against

market fluctuations, and 39 farmers (32.50%) called for more crops to be insured. Greater transparency from insurance agencies was urged by 38 farmers (31.67%), and 31 farmers (25.83%) suggested improving agency efficiency. Providing clear information on compensation calculations was requested by 23 farmers (19.17%), while 12 farmers (10.00%) emphasized the need for greater awareness through educational campaigns. These suggestions highlight the need for improvements in timely payments, compensation adequacy, uniform indemnity, expanded coverage, transparency, and awareness to enhance PMFBY's effectiveness.

Table 9: Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

Sr. no.	Suggestions	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Adequate Compensation	73	60.83	II
2	Timely Compensation	88	73.33	I
3	Transparency from Agencies	38	31.67	VII
4	Awareness of the Scheme	12	10.00	X
5	Complete Information on Compensation	23	19.17	IX
6	Improved Agency Operations	31	25.83	VIII
7	Uniform Indemnity for different regions and types of crops	63	52.50	III
8	A greater number of crops are covered.	39	32.50	VI
9	Claims should be distributed before the start of the next season.	59	49.17	IV
10	The insurance agency should offer insurance cover to include price guarantees.	47	39.17	V

Conclusion

The analysis reveals contrasting trends in crop insurance participation and claims, with Maharashtra experiencing growth during the kharif season, while national-level data and the Nanded district saw significant declines in the rabi season. These trends highlight the need for targeted interventions to enhance the uptake, coverage, and efficiency of crop insurance schemes. The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) has effectively stabilized income and reduced yield variability, but it faces challenges such as inadequate compensation, delayed payouts, insufficient crop loss assessment personnel, and poor coordination among stakeholders. Frequent policy changes and corruption further erode farmer trust. To improve PMFBY's effectiveness and encourage wider adoption, farmers recommend timely compensation, broader crop coverage, and greater transparency. Addressing these issues is essential for building trust, enhancing risk management, and ensuring the scheme's long-term success.

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